

GRUPPO NAZIONALE DI INGEGNERIA GEOTECNICA

ATTI DELL'INCONTRO ANNUALE DEI
RICERCATORI DI GEOTECNICA

GAETA - 4 ÷ 6 SETTEMBRE 2024

Editori: Paolo Croce, Giuseppe Modoni, Erminio Salvatore, Michela Arciero

Edizioni AGI, Roma
ISBN: 9 788897 517191

ATTI DELL'INCONTRO ANNUALE DEI RICERCATORI DI GEOTECNICA

Editore: Edizioni AGI, Roma

ISBN: 9 788897 517191

Pubblicato sul sito www.iarg24.it

14/10/2024

L'Incontro Annuale 2024 dei Ricercatori di Geotecnica si è svolto presso il Castello Angioino di Gaeta, sede distaccata dell'Università di Cassino e del Lazio Meridionale, dal 4 al 6 settembre. Durante l'incontro sono state presentate e discusse le note inviate dai Componenti del Gruppo Nazionale di Ingegneria Geotecnica (GNIG), suddivise in 5 sessioni:

- SESSIONE I Sperimentazione di laboratorio e modellazione costitutiva
(presidenti: proff. Claudia Vitone e Giuseppe Scarpelli)
- SESSIONE II Opere e sistemi geotecnici
(presidenti: proff. Laura Tonni e Vincenzo Pane)
- SESSIONE III Geotecnica sismica
(presidenti: proff. Rossella Massimino e Paolo Croce)
- SESSIONE IV Caratterizzazione geotecnica del sito e geotecnica ambientale
(presidenti: proff. Stefania Lirer e Claudio Scavia)
- SESSIONE V Stabilità dei pendii
(presidenti: proff. Stefania Lirer e Claudio Scavia)

Le note complessivamente presentate, in numero pari a 84, forniscono un quadro complessivo delle attività di ricerca svolte nelle diverse sedi universitarie italiane.

MECHANICAL BEHAVIOUR OF WELL-GRADED GRAVEL-RUBBER MIXTURES IN STATIC AND CYCLIC FIELDS

Abate Glenda

Università di Catania
glenda.abate@unict.it

Chiaro Gabriele

University of Canterbury
gabriele.chiaro@canterbury.ac.nz

Fiamingo Angela

Università di Catania
angela.fiamingo@unict.it

Massimino Maria Rossella

Università di Catania
maria.massimino@unict.it

Abstract

The necessity to repurpose End-of-Life Tires (ELTs) has driven researchers to seek new methods for converting them into useful products. Recently, shredded rubber from ELTs has been increasingly utilised in various civil engineering fields due to its valuable mechanical properties. Over the past few years, numerous experimental tests have been conducted on the use of shredded scrap tyres mixed with poorly-graded granular soil, primarily sand or gravel, as backfill material for retaining walls, liquefaction mitigation, structural fill, and geotechnical seismic isolation (GSI). Many studies in literature have focused on the mechanical properties of sand-rubber mixtures, while limited research has been done on the behaviour of gravel-rubber mixtures. This paper aims to explore the physical and mechanical properties of more economic and easy-to-prepare geomaterials combining well-graded gravel mixed with scrap rubber grains (wgGRMs) through isotropically consolidated drained monotonic and cyclic triaxial (TxCD and CLTxT) tests. The tests were carried out by varying the confining pressure and the volumetric rubber content (VRC). The results highlight the effect of confining pressure and VRC on the stress-strain relationship and volumetric and cyclic behaviour.

1. Introduction

The constant worldwide increase in End-of-Life Tires (ELTs) has highlighted the need to explore innovative solutions for incorporating waste rubber into civil engineering applications, aligning with the global sustainable development goals and circular economy (Agenda 2030). Waste rubber, whether used alone or in combination with other materials, is a low-cost and environmentally sustainable construction material (Tasalloti et al., 2021), having a low unit weight, bulk density, high hydraulic conductivity, high elastic deformability, and high damping ratio. Soil-rubber mixtures (SoRMs), primarily comprising sand or gravel, have recently been utilised as fill for embankments and retaining walls or as drainage layer (Hazarika et al., 2020). In addition, SoRMs can be adopted to mitigate dynamic motion (Geotechnical Dynamic Isolation, GDI, systems) as seismic motion (Tsang 2008; Pitilakis et al. 2021; Abate et al. 2023a-b) and anthropogenic vibrations (such as traffic, blasting, and machine foundations)

that affect existing and new structures and infrastructures.

Over the past decades, numerous studies have investigated the static and cyclic behaviour of sand-rubber mixtures (SRMs; Lee et al., 2007). Although gravel-rubber mixtures (GRMs) have been less extensively studied, they offer several advantages over SRMs, such as lower compressibility, higher permeability, and lower implementation costs (Hazarika et al., 2020). However, fewer studies have examined the behaviour of GRMs (Pasha et al., 2019; Chiaro et al., 2023), focusing on soil-rubber mixtures with poorly-graded soil fraction. Nevertheless, poorly-graded gravel is more challenging to obtain and then less economic than well-graded gravel. This paper aims to investigate the mechanical behaviour of mixtures made from well-graded gravel mixed with granulated rubber from ELTs (wgGRMs) through isotropically consolidated drained monotonic and cyclic triaxial (TxCD and CLTxT) tests. The tests were carried out at the Geotechnical Laboratory of the University of Canterbury (Christchurch, New Zealand). The results show the effects of confining pressure and volumetric rubber content (VRC) on the overall mechanical performance of wgGRMs in static and cyclic fields.

2. Materials and experimental tests

2.1 Tested materials

The mixtures were prepared using well-graded gravel (wgGRM 100/0, see Fig. 1a) with angular to subrounded grains, collected from a quarry near Christchurch (New Zealand), and pure granulated rubber from ELTs (wgGRM 0/100, see Fig. 1.b) with non-spherical grains. The selected gravel and rubber were mixed to obtain mixtures at different VRC of 25%, 40%, and 55% (labelled as wgGRM 75/25, wgGRM 60/40, and wgGRM 45/55, respectively). The particle size distribution curves for the investigated mixtures are shown in Fig. 1.c. The wgGRM 100/0 and wgGRM 0/100 had a mean grain size (D_{50}) of 5.78 mm and 5.35 mm, respectively, leading to an aspect ratio ($AR = D_{50,R} / D_{50,G}$) close to one. Laboratory tests were performed to evaluate the specific gravity and the maximum and minimum dry density of the tested wgGRMs (G_s , $\gamma_{d,min}$ and $\gamma_{d,max}$); the results are summarised in Table 1.

Fig 1. Materials tested: (a) well-graded gravel (wgGRM 100/0) and (b) granulated rubber (wgGRM 0/100); (c) particle size distribution curves of the tested mixtures.

2.2 Sample preparation and test procedure

TxCD and CLTxT tests were performed on specimens of 100 mm in diameter and 200 mm in height to investigate the mechanical behaviour of wgGRMs in static and cyclic fields. TxCD and CLTxT tests were carried out according to ASTM D7181-20 and JGS 0542-2009. Homogeneous samples were prepared using the under-compaction method (Ladd, 1978), considering a target degree of compaction equal to 95%. 3% water by weight was added to the mixture to generate suction and prevent rubber segregation. The well-graded gravel and granulated rubber were then carefully mixed by hand, placed

into a split mold, and compacted in 5 layers.

Mixture label	VRC (%)	G_s (-)	$\gamma_{d,min}$ (kN/m ³)	$\gamma_{d,max}$ (kN/m ³)
wgGRM 100/0	0	2.67	17.74	20.41
wgGRM 75/25	25	2.29	14.08	16.59
wgGRM 60/40	40	2.06	11.95	14.49
wgGRM 45/55	55	1.83	9.96	12.12
wgGRM 0/100	100	1.15	5.00	6.40

Table 1. Specific gravity (G_s), minimum and maximum unit weight ($\gamma_{d,min}$ and $\gamma_{d,max}$) of the tested wgGRMs having different volumetric rubber content (VRC).

The saturation of the samples, for the TxCD and CLTxT tests, was achieved by applying three methods of saturation in series: CO₂-method, water percolation, and application of the back pressure. Full saturation was assumed to be achieved when Skempton's B parameter was greater than 0.96.

The samples prepared for the TxCD tests were consolidated at effective confining pressures (σ'_3) of 30 kPa, 60 kPa, and 100 kPa. While, for the CLTxT tests described here, the samples were consolidated at σ'_3 equal to 100 kPa. TxCD tests were performed at a constant axial strain rate of 0.25%/min. CLTxT tests were conducted by applying 11 sinusoidal waves of cyclic axial load at a constant amplitude and frequency (0.05 Hz) for each loading step.

3. Results

3.1 TxCD test results

The effects of the confining pressure and VRC on the wgGRMs samples are depicted in Fig. 2, in terms of deviatoric stress-deviatoric strain behaviour (q - ε_q) and volumetric strain-deviatoric strain behaviour (ε_v - ε_q) under confining pressures of 30 kPa, 60 kPa, and 100 kPa.

The relative movements between grains are influenced by the confining pressure. Hard-grained soil particles can easily roll over and slip each other at lower confining pressures. As the confining pressure increases, the relative movements between grains decrease. More specifically, as expected, for wgGRM 100/0, an evident peak in deviatoric stress is followed by post-peak softening behaviour, for all the investigated confining pressures. Figs. 2.a, 2.b, and 2.c highlight that the peak deviatoric stress increases with higher confining pressure due to greater interlocking between grains. Figs. 2.d, 2.e, and 2.f point out that the increase of the confining pressure leads to a contractive response with reduced dilation tendency. The mechanical response of the wgGRM 75/25, wgGRM 60/40, and wgGRM 45/55 is closely related to the confining pressure and VRC. Specifically, the peak of the deviatoric stress becomes less pronounced with the decreasing of confining pressure and the increasing of VRC. The wgGRM 75/25 exhibits a strain-softening behaviour, especially at confining pressures of 60 kPa and 100 kPa, as highlight in Figs. 2.b and 2.c. wgGRM 60/40 and wgGRM 45/55 exhibit a strain-hardening behaviour for all the investigated confining pressures (Figs. 2.a, 2.b, and 2.c). wgGRM 75/25, wgGRM 60/40, and wgGRM 45/55 exhibit a contractive behaviour that becomes more evident with increasing VRC, with marginal dilation at higher deviatoric strains, as shown in Figs. 2.d, 2.e, and 2.f. Thus, the presence of the rubber causes the passage from the dilatative and softening behaviour typical of the well-graded gravel to a contractive and hardening behaviour, which is more evident as the VRC increases.

The shear straight angle (φ') for the wgGRMs was also evaluated. The well-graded gravel (wgGRM 100/0) shows the highest value of φ' (46°-50°) while wgGRM 45/55 has the lowest value of φ' (35°-41°). φ' almost linearly decreases with increasing VRC. However, for all the investigated mixtures, the values of the shear strength angles are greater than 30°; therefore, the investigated mixtures can generally guarantee a good shear strength. The Young's modulus (E_0) for the wgGRMs was also assessed. Specifically, wgGRM 100/0 and wgGRM 45/55 show the highest and lowest values of E_0 (84232-27028

kPa and 6661-3862 kPa), respectively. So, as expected, the value of E_0 is strictly linked to the VRC. The compressible nature of wgGRMs could lead to high settlements, so because of this, the behaviour of wgGRMs can be improved using reinforcements (geogrids) as proposed by Dhanya et al. (2020) for SRMs.

Fig 2. Response of wgGRMs in isotropically consolidated drained monotonic triaxial tests under 30, 60 and 100 kPa confining pressure (σ'_3): (a, b, c) deviatoric stress - deviatoric strain relationships; and (d, e, f) volumetric behaviours.

3.2 CLTxT test results

The results of the CLTxT tests under the confining pressure of 100 kPa will be discussed for wgGRM 75/25, wgGRM 60/40 and wgGRM 45/55, highlighting the effect of VRC. Fig. 3.a reports the trends of the secant shear modulus (G_{sec}) with the shear strain (γ) for the investigated mixtures. As it is known, G_{sec} decreases by increasing the shear strain; nevertheless, the G_{sec} decreasing becomes less significant as VRC increases, thus a more linear response is achieved with the increasing of the rubber content. The values of G_0 , reported in Fig. 3.a, were obtained by Bender Element Tests carried out previously on the same mixtures by the authors (Fiamingo, 2024). Fig. 3.b and 3.c report the variation of the normalised shear modulus ($G_{sec}/G_0(\gamma)$) and the damping ratio ($D(\gamma)$) with the shear strain, compared with the ranges experimentally observed on cohesionless soils by Seed et al. (1986) and Rollins et al. (1998), see dashed lines. The G_{sec}/G_0 curves for the tested wgGRMs (continuous lines) were obtained from the achieved experimental data fitted by the hyperbolic model proposed by Darendeli (2001). The experimental data for the $D(\gamma)$ curves were fitted using the model proposed by Yokota et al. (1981).

Regarding the G_{sec}/G_0 curves, an increase in VRC leads to a more linear shape. All the curves for the wgGRMs tested are located inside the ranges proposed by Seed et al. (1986) and Rollins et al. (1998), except for wgGRMs 45/55 for $\gamma > 0.1\%$. As regards the D curves, an increase in the rubber content leads to a more linear shape, too. For $\gamma < 0.01\%$, the D values for wgGRMs are greater than those for cohesionless soils and range from $D = 3.5\%$ for wgGRM 75/25 to $D = 6.7\%$ for wgGRM 45/55; then for $\gamma < 0.01\%$ the wgGRMs tested show a high energy absorption abilities. For $\gamma \geq 0.01\%$ (Fig. 3.c), an increase in VRC leads to a lower damping ratio. This phenomenon is also observed in the poorly-graded gravel-rubber mixtures tested by Pistolas et al. (2018) due to the increasing effect of the material grain dislocation. However, all the curves for the tested wgGRMs at $\gamma \geq 0.01\%$ are located inside the ranges by

Seed et al. (1986) and Rollins et al. (1998), showing values of D greater than about 10%.

Fig 3. Response of wgGRMs in isotropically consolidated drained cyclic triaxial tests under 100 kPa confining pressure (σ'_3): (a, b, c) variation of the secant shear modulus (G_{sec}), normalised secant shear modulus (G_{sec}/G_0) and damping ratio (D) with the shear strain (γ). G_{sec} data fitted by the hyperbolic model proposed by Darendeli (2001).

4. Conclusions

The present paper investigated the static and cyclic behaviour of innovative and economic geomaterials made from well-graded gravel mixed with granulated rubber from ELTs (wgGRMs) through isotropically consolidated drained monotonic and cyclic triaxial (TxCD and CLTxT) tests. The tests on the wgGRMs were performed considering a rubber content equal to 0%, 25%, 40% and 55% (wgGRM 100/0, wgGRM 75/25, wgGRM 60/40 and wgGRM 45/55).

The TxCD tests reveal that, for any confining pressure, the use of the rubber causes a decrease in the peak of deviatoric stress, leading to a hardening behaviour compared to the well-graded gravel. This effect becomes more marked as VRC increases. Considering the volumetric behaviour, the rubber induces a contractive behaviour with a marginal dilation at high deviatoric strain levels.

As regards the shear strength, wgGRM 100/0 shows the highest value of the shear strength angle (46° - 50°), while wgGRM 45/55 has the lowest value (35° - 41°). Although the sand and the fine fraction of the well-graded gravel-rubber mixtures decrease the shear strength, the shear strength angle remains greater than 30° , generally guaranteeing an excellent shear strength. The Young's modulus (E_0) of wgGRMs is linked to the VRC. The compressible nature of wgGRMs could lead to high settlements, so because of this, the behaviour of wgGRMs can be improved using reinforcements (such as geogrids).

As regards CLTxT tests, the results show that the reduction in the secant shear modulus with the shear strain becomes less significant as VRC increases. The normalised shear modulus and the damping ratio vs shear strains curves show a more linear trend increasing the rubber content. At low shear strains (less than 0.01%), the damping ratio is higher (3.5%-6.7%) than that of soil, highlighting the beneficial absorption properties of wgGRMs. At shear strain levels greater than 0.01%, an increase in VRC leads to a lower damping ratio; however, D values are high, ensuring good dissipative properties to the wgGRMs.

Based on the results obtained, the wgGRMs investigated show good mechanical properties in the static

and cyclic fields; thanks to their energy absorption properties, they can be efficiently proposed as GDI systems. Compared to the other soil portions used in the mixtures (such as the poorly-graded gravel), the wgGRMs permit a remarkable reduction in the costs linked to material availability, thanks to their graded nature compared to the uniform ones.

Acknowledgements

Financial support provided by the Research Project “CHANGES – Cultural Heritage Active Innovation for Sustainable Society” funded by PNNR “Piano Nazionale di Ripresa e Resilienza, Missione 4 “Istruzione e ricerca” – Componente 2 “Dalla ricerca all’impresa” – Investimento 1.3, finanziato dall’Unione europea – Next GenerationEU (Avviso n. 341 del 15.03.2022), SPOKE 6 “History, Conservation and Restoration of Cultural Cultural Heritage” (in Italian).

References

- Abate G., Fiamingo A., Massimino M.R. (2023a). “An eco-sustainable innovative geotechnical technology for the structures seismic isolation, investigated by FEM parametric analyses”, *Bull. Earthq. Eng.*, 21(10), 4851–4875.
- Abate G., Fiamingo A., Massimino, M.R. (2023b). “FEM investigation of full-scale tests on DSSI, including gravel-rubber mixtures as geotechnical seismic isolation”, *Soil Dyn. Earthq. Eng.*, 172, 108033.
- Agenda (2030) Transforming our world: the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development. United Nations General Assembly. See <https://www.refworld.org/docid/57b6e3e44.html> (accessed 11/08/2022).
- ASTM D7181-20, Standard Test Method for Consolidated Drained Triaxial Compression Test for Soils. ASTM International, West Conshohocken, PA.
- Chiaro G., Palermo A., Banasiak L., et al. (2023). “Seismic response of low-rise buildings with eco-rubber geotechnical seismic isolation (ERGSI) foundation system: numerical investigation”, *Bull. Earthq. Eng.*, 21(8), 3797-3821.
- Darendeli M.B. (2001). “Development of a new family of normalised modulus reduction and material damping curves”, PhD Dissertation, University of Texas at Austin.
- Dhanya, J.S., Boominathan, A., Banerjee, S. (2020). “Response of low-rise building with geotechnical seismic isolation system”, *Soil Dyn. Earthq. Eng.*, 136, 106187.
- Fiamingo, A. (2024). “An eco-sustainable geotechnical seismic isolation system in dynamic soil-structure interaction”, Doctoral dissertation, University of Catania (Italy).
- Hazarika H., Pasha S.M.K., Ishibashi I., et al. (2020). “Tire-chip reinforced foundation as liquefaction countermeasure for residential buildings”, *Soils Found.*, 60(2), 315-326.
- JGS 0542-2009. Method for cyclic triaxial test to determinate deformation properties of geomaterials. Japanese Geotechnical society standards.
- Ladd R.S. (1978). “Preparing test specimens using undercompaction”, *Geotechnical Testing Journal*, 1(1), 16-23.
- Lee J.S., Dodds J., Santamarina J.C. (2007). “Behavior of rigid-soft particle mixtures”, *Journal of Materials in Civil Engineering*, 19(2), 179-184.
- Pasha S.M.K., Hazarika H., Yoshimoto N. (2019). “Physical and mechanical properties of gravel-tire chips mixture (GTCM)”, *Geosynth. Int.*, 26(1), 92-110.
- Pistolas G.A., Anastasiadis A., Pitolakis K. (2018). “Dynamic behaviour of granular soil materials mixed with granulated rubber: Influence of rubber content and mean grain size ratio on shear modulus and damping ratio for a wide strain range”, *Innov. Infrastruct. Solut.*, 3, 1-14.
- Pitolakis D., Anastasiadis A., Vratsikidis A., et al. (2021). “Large-scale field testing of geotechnical seismic isolation of structures using gravel-rubber mixtures”. *Earthq Eng. Struct. Dyn.*, 50(10), 2712-2731.
- Rollins K.M., Evans M.D., Diehl N.B., William D., Daily III. (1998). “Shear modulus and damping relationships for gravels”, *J. Geotech. Geoenviron.*, 124(5), 396-405.
- Seed H.B., Wong R.T., Idriss I.M., Tokimatsu K. (1986). “Moduli and damping factors for dynamic analyses of cohesionless soils”, *J. Geotech. Eng.*, 112(11) 1016-1032.
- Tasalotti A., Chiaro G., Murali A., et al. (2021). “Recycling of end-of-life tires (ELTs) for sustainable geotechnical applications: a New Zealand perspective”, *Appl. Sci.*, 11(17), 7824.
- Tsang H.H. (2008). “Seismic isolation by rubber–soil mixtures for developing countries”, *Earthq Eng. Struct. Dyn.*, 37(2), 283–303.
- Yokota K., Imai T., Konno M. (1981). “Dynamic deformation characteristics of soils determined by laboratory tests”, *OYO Tec. Rep*, 3, 13-37.